

UOT 711.4

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ROAD OF VICTORY – RESTORATION OF CITIES AND VILLAGES OF KARABAKH

Abstract. Today, we can say with great joy and pride that Shusha, which was under occupation for 30 years, is now free. As the honored President Ilham Aliyev said, Shusha, the cultural soul of Azerbaijan, is being revived. After the end of World War II in 2020, by order of the President of the Republic, a plan for the socio-economic development of the liberated territories was developed. Expressways, airports, smart villages, green energy - the Republic of Azerbaijan, on the territory of long-suffering Karabakh, is not just actively implementing the “Great Return” program, but strives to make the region the most advanced part of the country.

Key words: victory, city, construction, transport routes, green energy.

Introduction. After the end of II Karabakh War in 2020, a plan for the socio-economic development of the liberated territories was developed by order of the President of the Republic. The regional development project includes the construction of new settlements, administrative, public and cultural facilities, transport routes, airports of international importance, etc. (fig.1).

The interpretation of the main material. One of these projects was the construction of a new highway to Shusha –“Victory Road” - “Zəfəryolu”. During the visit of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev and First Vice-President Mehriban Aliyeva to the liberated Fuzuli and Jabrail regions on November 16, 2020, the foundation of the highway from Fuzuli to Shusha “VICTORY ROAD” was laid, passing through the territory of the Fuzuli, Khojavend, Khojaly and Shusha regions, covering dozens of settlements, including the cities of Fuzuli and Shusha.

According to the state program “Revival” in Shusha, it is planned to build 23 residential buildings with 450 apartments for indigenous Shusha residents who were forced to leave. According to the development plan in Shusha, houses can only be up to 5 floors. Schools are being built, a hospital is being restored, and a mosque is being restored as part of the project. It was planned to resettle 1,500 residents of the first emigres by the end of 2023 (fig. 2, 3, 4, 5).

As a result of the occupation of Shusha, in order to erase the historical traces of Azerbaijanis, vandals destroyed about 600 historical architectural monuments, including the Palace of Panahali Khan, the Yukhari Govhar Agha Mosque, the Ashaghi Govhar Agha Mosque, the House of Khurshidbanu Natavan, the Mausoleum of Molla Panah Vagif, over 20 educational and cultural facilities, including 8 museums, among which are the Shusha Historical Museum and a branch of the Azerbaijan Carpet Museum, the only factory of eastern musical instruments in the Caucasus was destroyed, etc.

Shusha is a special place for Azerbaijan. It is called the spiritual center of the country; famous cultural figures of Azerbaijan lived here. The famous poet and statesman Molla Panah Vagif is among them. His mausoleum, which was built in the 1980s on the order by the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party – National Leader Heydar Aliyev, was destroyed during military operations. However, today it has been carefully restored thanks to Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev’s personal initiative (fig. 6,7,8).

Fuzuli, where the Victory Road begins, is entering a new stage. According to the developed project, about 50 thousand residents will live here. 2800 houses and other objects were restored in 22 settlements of the Fuzuli region as part of the Program for the Revival of the Liberated and Affected Territories as a result of the Occupation. Schools, hospitals, the Mil-Mughan reservoir, drinking water supply facilities and irrigation facilities have been restored. 16 secondary schools, roads, a market and several agricultural facilities have been restored with a grant from the European Commission. Approximately 1500 compatriots who returned to their ancestral lands are provided with permanent jobs.

Fuzuli will become a city built in accordance with new and modern standards.

According to the plans of the Azerbaijani government, Karabakh should become a zone of green energy and advanced technologies. It is assumed that the Zangilan region will become a center of innovation in the field of agriculture. The uniqueness of the settlement is that solar energy, wind

power and hydroelectric power stations will be used to support its life. For example, the villages of Aghali-I, II and III of Zangilan were designed and built according to the smart village system. And this is not the same as a smart home. The “Smart City” concept in Zangilan, Gubadli and Jabrail implies providing a modern quality of life for people through the use of innovative technologies, using all the locality’s own resources.

A project for the construction of smart villages – an analogue of a Belarusian agricultural town with an Azerbaijani flavor is being implemented on the territory of Karabakh (fig. 9,10).

A total of 41 families of former internally displaced persons (IDPs) returned to their native lands, to the village of Aghalion July 19, 2023.

The geographical location of the region and the opportunities available here create favorable conditions for the transformation of Zangilan into an international transport and logistics center. The international airport, which was completed in 2022, will play a big role in the future successful socio-economic development of Zangilan (fig.11).

This airport is the eighth international airport in Azerbaijan.

In total, three airports will operate on the liberated territories: the airport in Fuzuli was opened in September 2021, the airport in Zangilan was opened on October 20, 2022, and the Lachin airport will be completed in late 2024 – early 2025. The airport that will be built in Lachin is also of strategic importance. The construction of the airport will make it possible to use the tourist potential of Lachin and Kelbajar widely. It should be noted that the Lachin International Airport is one of the important elements of the travelling transport strategy by President Ilham Aliyev in the territories liberated from occupation (fig. 12,13).

Conclusion: Karabakh. Time to live and build. Highways, airports, smart villages, green energy –the Republic of Azerbaijan is not just actively implementing the “Great Return” program, but strives to make the region the most advanced part of the country on the territory of long-suffering Karabakh.

The construction of the Victory Road in a short time is a symbol of the bright Victory won by the Azerbaijani people. The restoration of road infrastructure not only ensures the unhindered movement of people to the liberated territories, but also expands the economic and tourism opportunities of the region. All this promises new prospects for the further development of these territories.

According to the plan of the First State Program “Great Return” of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2022–2025, there will be:

- 34500 apartments and individual houses will be built,
- general plans for seven cities will be approved,
- the Agdam - Khankendi gas pipeline and its branches will be built,
- 197 educational institutions and others will be built.

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ZƏFƏR YOLU – QARABAĞIN ŞƏHƏR VƏ KƏNDLƏRİNİN BƏRPASI

Bu gün böyük sevinc və qürurla deyirik ki, 30 il işğal altında olan Şuşa indi azaddır. Möhtərəm Prezident İlham Əliyevin dediyi kimi, Azərbaycanın mədəni ruhu olan Şuşa dirçəlir. Sürətli yollar, hava limanları, ağıllı kəndlər, yaşıl enerji – Azərbaycan Respublikası çoxdan əziyyət çəkən Qarabağ ərazisində nəinki “Böyük Qayıdış” proqramını fəal şəkildə həyata keçirir, həm də regionun ölkənin ən qabaqcıl bölgəsinə çevrilməsinə çalışır.

Açar sözlər: qələbə, şəhər, tikinti, nəqliyyat marşrutları, yaşıl enerji.

Самира Абдуллаева (Азербайджан)

ДОРОГА ПОБЕДЫ – ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЕ ГОРОДОВ И СЕЛ КАРАБАХА

Сегодня с большой радостью и гордостью мы говорим, что Шуша, которая 30 лет находилась под оккупацией, теперь свободна. Как сказал уважаемый президент Ильхам Алиев, Шуша – культурная душа Азербайджана возрождается. Скоростные трассы, аэропорты, умные поселки, зеленая энергетика — Азербайджанская Республика на территории многострадального Карабаха не просто активно реализует программу «Большое возвращение», а стремится сделать из региона самую передовую часть страны.

Ключевые слова: победа, город, строительство, транспортные магистрали, зеленая энергетика.

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Victory Road.

Fig. 2. Shusha after the occupation.

Fig. 3, 4. Residential buildings in Shusha will be like this.

Fig. 5. President IlhamAliyev and First lady MehribanAliyeva at the opening ceremony of “Karabakh” hotel in Shusha.

Fig. 6. Mausoleum, built in the 1980s on the order by National Leader Heydar Aliyev.

Fig. 7, 8. Mausoleum of the poet and statesman MollaPanahVagif. After restoration.

Fig. 9.The project for the village of Aghali

Fig. 10. Real construction of the village of Aghali

Fig. 11. Zangilan airport

Fig. 12, 13. Zangilan residents